

Opus-MontenegrinSubs 1.0: First electronic corpus of the Montenegrin language

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kon text Query Corpora Save Concordance Filter Frequency Collocations View Help

Corpus: Opus MontenegrinSubs: Montenegrin | Query: čudo (11 hits)

Hits: 11 | i.p.m. 23.74 (related to the whole "opusmonte_cnr") | ARF 6.96 | Result is sorted 1 / 1

Line selection: simple | Display options

	Opus MontenegrinSubs: Montenegrin	Opus MontenegrinSubs: English
☐	Damages.S1.dam0106... Ova terapeutkinja je napravila čuda .	Damages.S1.dam0106... This therapist did wonders for me.
☐	Damages.S1.dam0106... Čuda se događaju.	Damages.S1.dam0106... Miracles do happen.
☐	Damages.S2.dam0205... Čudo je da si preživio.	Damages.S2.dam0205... It's amazing that you survived.
☐	Damages.S2.dam0206... Nije čudo da nijesu otkrili ništa u vezi s ubistvom.	Damages.S2.dam0206... No wonder they haven't gotten anywhere with David's murder.
☐	Damages.S2.dam0207... Nije ni čudo što policija nije ni mrdnula u rješavanju Dejvidovog ubistva.	Damages.S2.dam0207... No wonder they haven't gotten anywhere with david's murder.
☐	Damages.S5.dam0507... Čuda digitalne tehnologije.	Damages.S5.dam0507... Wonders of digital technology.
☐	HoC.S1.hoc0305-cnr Izvela si čudo .	HoC.S1.hoc0305-en You made a miracle happen.
☐	Tudors.S1.tud0101-cnr Neki kažu da je osmo svjetsko čudo!	Tudors.S1.tud0101-en Some say it's the 8th wonder of the world!
☐	Tudors.S2.tud0206-cnr Navodno krv sveca, koja se koristi za liječenje hodočasnika, koji se okupljaju tamo nadajući se čudu , ispostavilo se da je krv patke, koju monasi redovno obnavljaju.	Tudors.S2.tud0206-en Supposedly the blood of a saint, used for healing the pilgrims who flock there hoping for a miracle, it turns out to be the blood of a duck, which the monks renew regularly.

NoSketch Engine | čudo | Opus MontenegrinSubs: Montenegrin | guest

Query **čudo** 11 > Filter by aligned corpus 11 (23.74 per million)

	Opus MontenegrinSubs: Montenegrin	Opus MontenegrinSubs: English
Damages.S1.dam0106-cnr	prvog suđenja. Ova terapeutkinja je napravila čuda . Nije važno šta je... Škripanje zubima,	Damages.S1.dam0106-en This /Dg therapist /Nc-s did /V-is wonders /Nc-p for /Sp me /Pp . /Z
Damages.S1.dam0106-cnr	... U ringu sa Peti Hjuz... I još stojimo. Čuda se događaju. Dobar si prijatelj, Rej. Hvala. To	Damages.S1.dam0106-en Miracles /Nc-p do /V-ip happen /V-b . /Z
Damages.S2.dam0205-cnr	. Divno... I čestitke tebi... Deset godina. Čudo je da si preživio. Samo zbog ove ovdje. Oprosti	Damages.S2.dam0205-en It /Pp 's /V-ip3s amazing /A-p that /Sp you /Pp survived /V-is . /Z
Damages.S2.dam0206-cnr	je i vjerovatno je radio za Frobišera. Nije čudo da nijesu otkrili ništa u vezi s ubistvom. To je	Damages.S2.dam0206-en No /Rgp wonder /V-ip they /Pp have /V-ip n't /Rgp gotten /V-ps anywhere /Rgp with /Sp David /Np-s 's /Ss murder /Nc-s . /Z
Damages.S2.dam0207-cnr	je policajac. Mora da radi za Frobišera. Nije ni čudo što policija nije ni mrdnula u rješavanju	Damages.S2.dam0207-en No /Rgp wonder /V-ip they /Pp have /V-ip n't /Rgp gotten /V-ps anywhere /Rgp with /Sp david /Nc-s 's /Ss murder /Nc-s . /Z